

Nexus between Renewable Energy, Environmental Innovation, Trade and environmental sustainability in Russia and India

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Abstract: The study's motivation is to investigate the EKC hypothesis with the nexus between environmental sustainability, renewable energy, environmental innovation and trade in Russia and India from 1980-to 2018. Several econometric tools were applied to gauge the nexus, such as linear and nonlinear unit root tests, Bayer and Hacked combined cointegration test, ARDL and NARDL for discovering symmetry and symmetry effects on environmental sustainability and non-granger causality test for directional association. Furthermore, the study performed Fully-modified OLS, Dynamic OLS and Canonical Cointegrating Regression (CCR) for empirical estimation robustness. Variables properties assessment with unit root test established order of integration after first difference and nonlinearity confirmed with nonlinear unit root tests. The long-run association in the empirical model was established with Bayer and Hacked cointegration test, Fpass, Wpass and tBDM test. For the KEC test, the coefficients of Y^2 were exposed negative statistically significant association with environmental sustainability in both countries. Thus Our empirical analysis validates the EKC hypothesis for both Russia and India. According to ARDL estimation, renewable energy and environmental innovation have negative. In contrast, trade is positively associated with environmental sustainability in Russia and India. Moreover, the standard Wald test confirmed asymmetric association both in the long and short run. Our empirical approach allows us to encourage policymakers in Russia and India to introduce sector-specific environmental reforms, provide continuous support to environmental technologies, reduce subsidies on nonrenewable energy and introduce green trade policies to procure sustainable development.

Keywords: EKC hypothesis; Renewable energy; Energy innovation; Russia; India; Environmental sustainability;

Introduction

According to Grossman and Krueger (1991), an inverted U-shaped relationship exists between per capita income and environmental degradation. As per capita income rises, environmental degradation rises to a maximum but then falls, and the turning point is the critical high level of income. The nexus between economic growth and carbon emission has been extensively discussed in the existing literature. [Grossman and Krueger \[1\]](#), [Grossman and Helpman \[2\]](#) were the first to investigate such issues. They reported that economic progress leads to environmental degradation, followed by subsequent environmental improvement, later termed as Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) [\[3\]](#). The EKC hypothesis considers the association between a deterioration in environmental quality and environmental pollution, especially in recent years. [Panayotou \[3\]](#) indicated that economic growth has three distinct effects over carbon emissions/environmental pollution: scale, technical and structural, and scale effects. The scale effects explain that energy consumption leads to higher emissions given a certain

level of technology to achieve economic goals. The structural effect narrates that structural transformation during economic development affects environmental degradation as higher polluting industries are replaced by low polluting industries, reducing carbon emissions during the manufacturing process. Last, the technical effects explain that despite achieving economic expansion, carbon emissions during manufacturing are reduced mainly due to technological innovation and progress.

There are more than 3400 EKC research publications in the web of science database. Nearly 500 were published alone in 2020 [4], where the EKC hypothesis has been extensively explored from the following four aspects: environmental regulations, technical progress, foreign direct investment and international trade [5-7]. However, there is a higher focus on investigating the association between GHG emissions and cleaner energy sources. [Koirala, Dhakal \[8\]](#) incorporated an empirical strategy to review the role of renewable energy while investigating the EKC hypothesis to conclude that environmental degradation has a significant correlation with economic and industrial policies and clean energy sources are crucial to ensure environmental quality. Recent economic literature has further explored such associations to claim that carbon emissions are significantly lowered after introducing renewable energy into the energy mix.

The current study investigates the EKC hypothesis for India and Russia. Due to the shift from central planning towards free-market economic reforms, they are among the fastest-growing economies in the middle east and north African region. In recent decades, Russia and India have accelerated structural reforms to restructure and liberalize economic and financial sectors to achieve economic goals through Structural Adjustment Programs (SAPs). The opening of the domestic economy was also accelerated as European Union became a major trading partner for both countries through multiple accords (73.18% and 72% for Russia and India, respectively[9]). Furthermore, both of these countries have become the preferred destination of FDI among the most preferred nations. As a result, both countries compete to become the most attractive environment for foreign investors through a qualified workforce, developed infrastructure, stable economic policies, and better political stability. Other channels might also be explored to examine the interrelation between India and Russia's economies, such as imports, foreign direct investment (FDI) flows, and financial linkages. Regarding FDI, although these flows are generally direct volatile, we consider that foreign direct investment behavior is generally considered a structural nature, where its most significant impact can be observed between medium to long term periods. It is less appropriate for an empirical strategy based on business cycle correlations[10].

The novelty of this study lies in the following aspects. First, our best knowledge is the first-ever study for investigating the KEC hypothesis with environmental sustainability, renewable energy consumption, and environmental innovation in Russia and India. However, several studies have been initiated in literature by taking into account another economy. Second, we investigated the KEC hypothesis by applying symmetric and asymmetric frameworks following [Pesaran, Shin \[11\]](#) and [Shin, Yu \[12\]](#). Our study findings validated the KEC in Russia and India with symmetric and asymmetric assessment. Regarding variables elasticity to environmental sustainability, the study suggested that renewable energy and environmental innovation mitigate environmental degradation by reducing carbon emissions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows; Section II deals with a literature survey on the association between environmental sustainability, economic growth, renewable energy consumption and energy innovation. Section III outlines empirical model and econometric strategy, section IV narrates empirical findings, and section V details concluding remarks and Implications.

2. Literature review

Since the industrial revolution, there has been a steady increase in global carbon emissions mainly due to increasingly higher reliance on fossil fuels to achieve economic transformation. Consequently, global emission levels have reached more than 36 billion tonnes, 1.6 times higher than

1990. Furthermore, this has also contributed to the rise of global average temperature in recent decades [13-15], adversely affecting humans and other species alike. Consequently, there is greater awareness to investigate the association between carbon emissions and global climate change. Academic researchers and policymakers have paid significant attention to assessing how carbon emissions affect climate change in different economic demographics. The global energy supply has reached 13.7 billion tons of oil equivalent to economic goals, and fossil fuels contributed to more than 80% of total energy consumption. In comparison, despite having low carbon emissions and recent environmental reforms, the share of renewable energy sources is still less than 20%, which is even significantly lower in developing economies and is an effective alternative to reduce environmental degradation from carbon emissions [16].

Current economic literature has extensively discussed the linkage between trade, renewable energy, economic growth, innovation in environmental technologies, and carbon emission. A portion of research projects has investigated the inner-relationship amongst CO₂ emissions as a measure of environmental sustainability and the variables above. [Mhenni \[17\]](#) empirically explored the EKC hypothesis using GMM methodology from 1980 to 1997; the researcher examined carbon emissions, vehicles, and fertilizer concentration to conclude that the EKC hypothesis is not proven for environmental pollutants. [Chebbi, Olarreaga \[18\]](#) relied on a concentration empirical approach to examine how trade openness, per capita CO₂ emissions, and economic growth influence each other. The empirical findings specified that carbon emissions, trade openness, and economic growth granger cause one another; further analysis forecasted short-run causal association amongst trade openness and carbon emissions. In an earlier study, [Belloumi \[19\]](#) researched how economic growth is influenced by energy consumption through the Johansen cointegration approach to indicate the bidirectional causal association between economic growth and energy consumption in the long run. [Fodha and Zaghdoud \[20\]](#) also used the causality analysis approach to analyze how economic policies and carbon emissions influence the environmental deterioration in developing economies. The application of VECM and Johansen causality analysis indicated unidirectional causal association from economic growth to carbon emissions in short and long-run empirical findings. Taking into account the empirical nexus, we reported the literature findings with three subgroups[21].

First, The pursuit of greater economic development is inextricably linked to energy security and environmental degradation. Energy is a necessary input for economic activity; nevertheless, excessive energy use puts more strain on the environment, either via by-product pollutants or the depletion of natural resources. Economic growth should be accomplished in sustainability while efforts are made to protect the environment to preserve its usefulness for future generations. The environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) hypothesizes that economic growth, rather than being detrimental to the environment, improves environmental indicators, ultimately leading to sustainable development. [Khan, Yu \[22\]](#) assess the role of renewable energy on trade and environment quality in Nordic counties from 2001 to 2018 by applying cross-sectional dependency, Panel unit root tests and dynamic CCE. Study findings reveal positive influence running from renewable energy consumption to trade liberalization and environmental quality. As far as policy intention, the study advocated that renewable energy integration in the economy offers economic sustainability through domestic trade expansion, environmental quality improvement and an eco-friendly ecosystem. [Busu and Nedelcu \[23\]](#) investigate the role of clean energy on the environmental sustainability of EU countries. Study findings documented a negative statistically significant association in empirical nexus, suggesting that Clean energy integration through biofuel and renewable energy is directly connected with reducing CO₂ level in another study [Shafiei and Salim \[24\]](#) documented a positive role between nonrenewable energy and carbon emission and negative association between renewable energy and CO₂. [Ben Jebli, Ben Youssef \[25\]](#) investigates the KEC hypothesis by taking into account the role of renewable and nonrenewable energy consumption on the environment of 25 OECD countries for the period 1980-2018. Empirical estimation with FMOLS validated the KEC hypothesis and established a positive association between nonrenewable energy consumption and environmental degradation[26].

Second, Environmental degradation is a significant problem in economics and has garnered substantial attention from various academics and economists over the last few decades. Countries are confronted with serious global warming issues as a result of the continued rise in carbon emissions. Numerous causes that contribute to environmental deterioration have been discovered lately, and governments are attempting to address these issues that affect environmental quality. Environmental deterioration has been a major concern for nations globally in recent years as carbon emissions have increased. Environmental sustainability is a critical issue for nations; yet, the discussion about the role of innovation and institutions in achieving environmental sustainability is still insufficient. There is a dearth of knowledge about how countries may accomplish both economic development and environmental protection. Innovation is seen as a successful strategy since it improves energy efficiency and produces greener products, thus lowering carbon emissions.

[Mongo, Belaïd \[27\]](#) investigated the impact of environmental innovation on environmental degradation by taking a panel of 15 EU nations over 23 years by employing ARDL in panel form. The study established a positive impact in reducing carbon emission in the long run, but rebound effects were revealed in the short run.

Third, According to economic theory, trade liberalization between nations with varying levels of environmental protection can lead to pollution-intensive industries concentrating in countries with lower environmental regulations (Baumol and Oates, 1988). This impact is known as the pollution haven effect, and it is the most contentious area of discussion when it comes to TL and the environment. In the economic literature, there is no consensus on whether the pollution haven effect exists or not. Suppose one country internalizes the social cost of the environment and does not include the environment in international commerce. In that case, the last country has a comparative advantage in items with high environmental costs [\[28\]](#). The linking between trade openness and environmental quality has been extensively studied via the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) paradigm by examining the relationship between per capita income and inequality [\[1\]](#). According to the Environmental Kuznets Curve theory, transitional nations may achieve sustainable economic development after reaching a certain level of per capita income.

Additionally, trade openness is a key element in assisting transitional countries to simultaneously reduce carbon dioxide emissions and increase economic development via a combination of size, composition, and method impacts. Moreover, Trade openness can be viewed as a critical element affecting environmental quality and regulatory compliance. Numerous studies have been conducted to determine the effect of trade openness on CO₂ emissions. According to [Antweiler, Copeland \[29\]](#), trade openness can impact environmental quality via scale, composition, and technique effects. The influence of trade openness on environmental quality may be classified into three categories: size, composition, and method [\[2\]](#). Economic development resulting from trade results in a rise in pollutant emissions due to increased energy consumption and cross-border transportation services. The composition effect is brought about by a company's decision to specialize in a certain industry to gain a competitive edge. This impact varies by competitive advantage source. Due to trade liberalization, the technique's impact results from technology flowing into less-developed nations [\[30\]](#).

Existing literature two lines of evidence have suggested regarding the role of trade openness and environmental degradation. First, a growing number of researchers advocated the positive role of trade openness on environmental degradation see [Managi, Hibiki \[31\]](#), [Ahmar and del Val \[32\]](#), [Park, Meng \[33\]](#), [\[34\]](#). In a study, [Ling, Ahmed \[35\]](#) postulated that trade openness offering technological efficiency positively correlated with environmental quality by lower carbon emission in the ecosystem. It is due to trade openness-led innovation increase technical effects and reduce scale effects in aggregate output.

The second line of empirical studies established an adverse association between trade and environmental degradation see [Nasir and Rehman \[36\]](#), [Shahbaz, Nasreen \[37\]](#), [Zameer, Yasmeen \[38\]](#).

In a study, [Dean \[39\]](#) postulated that trade harms pollution emissions, resulting in environmental deterioration. However, it also lowers pollution emission growth via the income effect, resulting in a beneficial impact on the environment.

3. Data and Model

Variables and descriptive statistics

As previously mentioned in the introduction and literature review, we have included renewable energy consumption, and environmental innovation in the empirical approach as these factors not only eases ecological pressure but also decreases the share of fossil fuels in the energy mix to sustain the impact of environmental reforms especially in the developing economies. Finally, we have included the total volume of international trade as it is a better instrument to measure the impact of industrial and economic activities on environmental degradation [\[40\]](#). Higher international trade volumes can result in severe ecological problems through higher energy consumption, industrial and public infrastructure development, and consistent dependence on fossil fuels as an energy source. On the other hand, international trade can also reduce environmental externalities through energy efficiency, innovative technology, and economies of scale.

The motivation of the study is to evaluate the nexus between environmental sustainability (ES), renewable energy (RE), environmental innovation (EI), and trade with the presence of KEC in India and Russia for the period . the generalized function in empirical assessment as follows:

$$ES \int Y, Y^2, RE, EI, TR \quad (1)$$

Environmental sustainability is measured by carbon emission intensity, and RE is denoted for renewable energy consumption; EI explained the level of environmental innovation and TR for total trade. After taking the natural logarithm of research units and transform into long-run assessment in the following manner:

$$\ln ES_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln Y_t + \beta_2 \ln Y^2_t + \beta_3 \ln RE_t + \beta_4 \ln EI_t + \beta_5 \ln TR_t + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

Table I Variables definition, sources and expected sign

Variables	Definition	Notation	Sources	Expected sign
Environmental sustainability	Measured by per capita CO2 emissions	ES	WDI	
Economic growth	GDP per capita	Y	WDI	+
		Y ²	WDI	-
Environmental Innovation	Patents on environmental technologies	EI	OECD	-
Renewable energy		RE	WDI	-
Trade	Total trade volume (Sum of total import and export)	TR	WDI	+/-

Environmental sustainability, by following existing literature such as [Khan, Weili \[41\]](#), [Jiang and Ma \[42\]](#), is measured by CO2 emission (metric tons per capita). Literature postulated that environmental sustainability can be achieved by a low degree of carbon emission; thus, lower carbon economies have possessed better environmental quality. Renewable energy consumption, according to [Khan, Weili \[43\]](#), plays a critical role in enhancing environmental quality through carbon emission decreases. From an ecological perspective, renewable energy extension support establishes an ecofriendly environment with low carbon integration [\[44\]](#). Additionally, we assume that renewable energy from renewable sources will harm carbon emissions based on past research. Nonrenewable energy is energy derived from fossil fuels, which increases carbon emissions in the majority of countries. Our empirical estimation incorporated energy innovation measured by patent application for green

technological development, known as environmental innovation[45]. The association between innovation and environmental improvements has exhibited positive linkage, suggesting that environmental innovation allows energy efficiency, thus eventually decreasing carbon emission and moving to environmental sustainability. Total trade measured by the sum of total expo rt and improt. The descriptive statistics of research units displayed in

	ES	Y	RE	EI	TR
Panel –A for Russia					
Mean	13.30576	6574.143	3.602237	10.37888	53.61970
Median	11.12114	4994.066	3.602040	10.70899	51.64352
Maximum	26.89927	15974.64	4.038096	15.59000	110.5771
Minimum	9.605895	1330.757	3.227796	2.370000	26.25670
Std. Dev.	5.516448	4422.016	0.189496	2.193905	12.79785
Skewness	1.929790	0.659634	0.075355	-1.298372	2.295341
Kurtosis	4.970760	2.124046	2.896117	7.324000	12.46061
Jarque-Bera	28.17038	3.761641	0.050257	38.16009	165.8664
Probability	0.000001	0.152465	0.975184	0.000000	0.000000
Panel –B for India					
Mean	1.029635	864.3880	48.32269	7.134816	32.28183
Median	0.908602	508.8567	48.42081	6.875000	30.05055
Maximum	1.799825	2100.751	58.65286	11.24000	55.79372
Minimum	0.543977	296.4352	36.02122	2.800000	12.21927
Std. Dev.	0.372336	607.5317	6.101245	2.412017	14.13899
Skewness	0.658441	0.740260	-0.423250	0.129980	0.136875
Kurtosis	2.178882	2.023826	2.498295	1.803859	1.652436
Jarque-Bera	13.612619	4.717281	11.452405	22.247500	20.836303

Model specification

The current study attempts to investigate the EKC hypothesis and the role of renewable energy, energy innovation, and international trade towards carbon emissions in Russia and India through the following log model:

$$\ln CO_{2t} = \vartheta_0 + \vartheta_1 \ln Y_t + \vartheta_2 \ln Y_t^2 + \vartheta_3 \ln RE_t + \vartheta_4 \ln EI_t + \vartheta_5 \ln TR_t + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

In the equation mentioned above, $\ln CO_2$ is taken as a proxy for environmental degradation, $\ln Y$ is the level of economic growth, $\ln Y^2$ is the nonlinear term to investigate the EKC hypothesis. $\ln RE$ represents renewable energy consumption, $\ln EI$ represents the level of environmental innovation in the environmental industry, $\ln TR$ refers to volumes of international trade, and ϵ accounts for the error term. The pursuit of economic progress has put extra pressure on energy consumption and infrastructure development, which has led to significant environmental challenges in CO₂ emissions. Additionally, we include GDP^2 as it is a major contributor in alleviating ecological problems [10, 46].

Economical strategy

Unit root test

In an empirical investigation, the detection of variables stationary properties has been extensively considered due to appropriate model selection critical guided by research variables order of integration[44]. We employed both conventional tests of stationary by performing ADF test [47], P-P test [48], KPSS test [49] and nonlinear unit root tests by following Kruse [50] and Kapetanios, Shin [51]. furthermore, unit root with structural break was implemented by following Zivot and Andrews [52]

Combined cointegration test

In recent period detecting the long-run association among variables, research has been extensively applying the newly introduced cointegration test commonly known as combined cointegration, familiarized by [Bayer and Hanck \[53\]](#) over conventional cointegration tests such as [Engle and Granger \[54\]](#), [Johansen \[55\]](#) and [Banerjee, Dolado \[56\]](#). [Bayer and Hanck \[53\]](#) produced a combined cointegration test based on several cointegration approaches. This approach provides joint statistics to test the null of no-cointegration for more comprehensive results. If the null is rejected, no alternative is accepted that supports the existence of cointegration. The proposed combined cointegration test can achieve consistent and trustworthy cointegration findings by merging all non-cointegrating experiments. Due to numerous testing methods, this cointegration test gives accurate predictions while being computationally efficient. This indicates that the use of non-combining cointegration tests yields more reliable and efficient findings when compared to the use of individual t-tests or system-based tests, as previously stated. Following [Bayer and Hanck \[53\]](#), the combination of the computed significance level (p -value) of the individual cointegration test in this article is in Fisher's formula as follows:

$$EG - JOH = -2 [\ln(P_{EG}) + (P_{JOH})] \quad (3)$$

$$EG - JOH - BO - BDM = -2[\ln(P_{EG}) + (P_{JOH}) + (P_{BO}) + (P_{BDM})] \quad (4)$$

The possible p -values of several individual cointegration tests to be extracted from [Engle and Granger \[54\]](#), [Johansen \[57\]](#), [Peter Boswijk \[58\]](#) and [Banerjee, Dolado \[56\]](#) P_{EG} , P_{JOH} , P_{BO} and P_{BDM} , respectively. To get evidence regarding the long-run association, the calculated F-stat has to be greater than the critical value proposed by [Bayer and Hanck \[53\]](#) is the rejection of the null hypothesis "no cointegration."

ARDL and NARDL

We performed extensive unit root analysis to begin the econometric analysis as it is a prerequisite for cointegration and causality analysis. After confirming the variables' integration order of the ARDL and NARDL methodologies, i.e., data series is stationary at level or first difference, we applied nonlinear and linear cointegration analysis.

For main empirical analysis, we have selected asymmetric nonlinear) Furthermore, symmetric (linear) ARDL approaches. The primary reason for selecting these methodologies is that ARDL and NARDL are flexible and can be used where variables are integrated at level or first difference and suitable for small samples. ARDL requires appropriate lag selection as it can be used to eliminate the issue of endogeneity. Furthermore, a suitable lag length can address the occurrence of multicollinearity in the asymmetric ARDL [\[12\]](#). The application of ARDL provides us with long and short-run empirical results, all together and the lagged ECT provides information about long-run equilibrium's convergence. Bearing this in mind, we transform equation one into the following ARDL model:

$$\Delta(\ln ES_2)_t = \sigma_0 + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_{\alpha k} \Delta(\ln ES_2)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{bk} \Delta(\ln Y)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{ck} \Delta(\ln Y^2)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{dk} \Delta(RE)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{ek} \Delta(EI)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{fk} \Delta(TR)_{t-k} + \beta_1 (ES_2)_{t-1} + \beta_2 (\ln Y)_{t-1} + \beta_3 (\ln Y^2)_{t-1} + \beta_4 (RE)_{t-1} + \beta_5 (EI)_{t-1} + \beta_6 (TR)_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (3)$$

Where $\beta_{\alpha, b, c, d, e, f}$, $\beta_{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6}$, Δ and μ_t are used to explain short-run coefficients, long-run coefficients, first difference operator, and the error term, respectively. Before applying the ARDL approach, we used AIC (Akaike information criteria) to select the appropriate lag length. The null hypothesis of $H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = \beta_6 = 0$ articulates the absence of cointegration in the empirical analysis, whereas $H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq \beta_5 \neq \beta_6 \neq 0$ is used to indicate cointegration among the variables. Our selection of the bounds tests produce f -statistics, which is compared against the critical values to decide the presence of cointegration. After calculating the cointegration, we use the symmetric ARDL approach to calculate long-run dynamics.

As equation 2 already illustrates negative and positive changes in renewable energy ($\ln RE^+$, $\ln RE^-$), environmental innovation ($\ln EI^+$, $\ln EI^-$) and trade ($\ln TR^+$, $\ln TR^-$). We used negative and positive changes to specify partial sum as:

$$\ln RE^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \ln RE_i^+ + \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta \ln RE_i, 0) \quad (4)$$

$$\ln RE^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \ln RE_i^- + \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta \ln RE_i, 0) \quad (5)$$

$$\ln EI^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \ln EI_i^+ + \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta \ln EI_i, 0) \quad (6)$$

$$\ln EI^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \ln EI_i^- + \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta \ln EI_i, 0) \quad (7)$$

$$\ln TR^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \ln TR_i^+ + \sum_{i=1}^t \max(\Delta \ln TR_i, 0) \quad (8)$$

$$\ln TR^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \ln TR_i^- + \sum_{i=1}^t \min(\Delta \ln TR_i, 0) \quad (9)$$

Next, we follow the empirical approach suggested by Shin et al. (2014) to construct a nonlinear ARDL approach as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\ln CO_2)_t = & \sigma_0 + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_{\alpha k} \Delta(\ln CO_2)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{bk} \Delta(\ln GDP)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{ck} \Delta(\ln GDP^2)_{t-k} + \\ & \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{dk} \Delta(\ln RE^+)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{ek} \Delta(\ln RE^-)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{fk} \Delta(\ln EI^+)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{gk} \Delta(\ln RE^-)_{t-k} + \\ & \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{hk} \Delta(\ln TR^+)_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \beta_{jk} \Delta(\ln TR^-)_{t-k} + \beta_1 (CO_2)_{t-1} + \beta_2 (\ln GDP)_{t-1} + \beta_3 (\ln GDP^2)_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_4 (\ln RE^+)_{t-1} + \beta_5 (\ln RE^-)_{t-1} + \beta_6 (\ln EI^+)_{t-1} + \beta_7 (\ln EI^-)_{t-1} + \beta_8 (\ln TR^+)_{t-1} + \beta_9 (\ln TR^-)_{t-1} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The non-ARDL approach primarily relies on the bound test to investigate nonlinear cointegration. While, the decision criteria for cointegration, alternative and null hypothesis are similar to the linear ARDL. After investigating cointegration, we devise equation (11) to investigate the asymmetric effects of the variables included on the CO₂. Furthermore, we applied several diagnostics models to investigate the stability of symmetric and asymmetric models. We also used the WALD test to confirm that both regressor's asymmetric effects are significant.

Non-granger causality test

Lastly, we proceeded with the non-granger causality test to identify the causal association between variables through the following model:

$$\begin{aligned} ES_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{1i} ES_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \beta_{2j} ES_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_{1i} REC_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \gamma_{1j} REC_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \varphi_{1i} EY_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \varphi_{1j} EI_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} Y_{vol_{t-i}} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} Y_{vol_{t-j}} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} TR_{vol_{t-i}} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} TR_{vol_{t-j}} \\ & + \varepsilon_{1t} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} REC_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{1i} REC_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \beta_{2j} REC_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_{1i} ES_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \gamma_{1j} ES_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \varphi_{1i} EY_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \varphi_{1j} EI_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} Y_{vol_{t-i}} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} Y_{vol_{t-j}} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} TR_{vol_{t-i}} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} TR_{vol_{t-j}} \\ & + \varepsilon_{1t} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} EI_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{1i} EI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \beta_{2j} EI_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_{1i} REC_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \gamma_{1j} REC_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \varphi_{1i} ES_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \varphi_{1j} ES_{t-j} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} Y_{vol_{t-i}} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} Y_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} TR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} TR_{t-j} + \varepsilon_{1t} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{1i} Y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \beta_{2j} Y_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_{1i} REC_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \gamma_{1j} REC_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \varphi_{1i} EI_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \varphi_{1j} EI_{t-j} \\
& + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} ES_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} ES_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} TR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} TR_{t-j} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
TR_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{1i} TR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \beta_{2j} TR_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_{1i} REC_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \gamma_{1j} REC_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \varphi_{1i} EI_{t-i} \\
& + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \varphi_{1j} EI_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} ES_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} ES_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{1i} ES_{t-i} + \sum_{j=k+1}^{d_{max}} \delta_{2j} ES_{t-j} \\
& + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

5. Model Estimation and Interpretation

We begin our results and discussion section by explaining the findings of unit root tests. For the current study, we have relied on ADF [47], PP [59] unit root tests, GF-DLS, and KPSS [49] unit root tests. The findings in Table 1 illustrate that all variables for Russia and India are non-stationary at level but are stationary at the first difference, which indicates the stationary level of 1(1).

Table II Results of conventional unit root test

	ADF	GF-DLS	PP	KPSS		ADF	GF-DLS	PP	KPSS
EPU	-1.28	-0.331	-2.332	0.8460	ΔES	-6.412	-4.351	-4.959	0.0970
FDI	-2.128	-0.375	-2.482	0.9280	ΔRE	-6.691	-2.459	-5.875	0.1110
FD	-1.626	-1.613	-2.538	0.7760	ΔEI	-5.24	-3.512	-5.199	0.1770
TR	-2.074	-0.205	-0.34	0.8400	ΔTR	-6.596	-3.071	-4.974	0.1820
Y	-0.072	-0.381	-0.51	0.7740	ΔY	-5.002	-4.986	-4.514	0.0970
EPU	-7.182	-4.795	-5.29	0.1490	EPU	-6.179	-4.639	-3.532	0.1790
FDI	-4.845	-3.964	-4.296	0.1170	FDI	-5.845	-3.779	-3.857	0.1190
FD	-4.902	-4.081	-5.498	0.1760	FD	-7.216	-4.781	-3.108	0.1750
GCF	-5.769	-3.456	-3.271	0.1300	GCF	-6.668	-4.218	-4.415	0.1280
TO	-7.454	-3.586	-5.53	0.1300	TO	-7.092	-4.75	-5.345	0.1000
Y	-6.491	-2.659	-5.864	0.1060	Y	-7.064	-3.821	-4.772	0.1580

The next study evaluates stationary properties with structural break by following [Zivot and Andrews \[52\]](#). The results of structural break unit root tests display in

Table III. According to test statistics, research units are stationary after the first difference with one structural break in Russia (India), in particular, for the series of environmental sustainability in 2013 (2016), renewable energy in 2017 (2015), environmental innovation in 2014 (1999), total trade in 2015(2004)

Table III Results of structural break unit root test

	Russia				India				
	At level		After first difference		At level		After first difference		
ES	-2.79	2015	-7.135***	2010	ES	-2.369	2011	-8.936***	2016
Y	-3.066	2011	-5.424***	2017	Y	-2.072	2017	-8.558***	2015
RE	-2.655	2001	-5.272***	2007	RE	-2.847	2002	-8.58***	1999
EI	-3.001	2011	-6.747***	2014	EI	-2.771	2009	-5.581***	1999
TR	-2.747	1999	-7.332***	2015	TR	-2.611	2008	-8.249***	2001

Furthermore, the study performed a nonlinear unit root test following [Kapetanios, Shin \[51\]](#) and [Kruse \[50\]](#) to establish the possible nonlinearity in research units. The nonlinear unit root test results are displayed in. study findings detected that the test statistics are statistically significant at an a1% or 5% level of significance, suggesting the existence of nonlinearity in research units. The conclusion of nonlinear stationarity has validated by both tests.

Table IV Results of nonlinear unit root test

Series		ES	Y	EI	RE	TR
Case -1	Russia	-4.751***	-0.718	-2.157	-6.277***	-3.112**
	India	-2.751***	-3.124**	0.126	-6.522***	3.246
Case -2	Russia	-2.517***	-6.774***	-9.654**	6.849	-11.672***
	India	-2.728***	-3.373***	-7.528***	6.142	6.214
Case -3	Russia	-4.517***	-6.782***	-9.124***	7.363***	-10.890***
	India	-2.013*	-3.171**	-9.210**	7.634***	-6.811***
Critical value Kapetanios, Shin [51]						
	level	Case-1	Case-2	Case -3		
	1%	-2:82	-3:48	-3:93		
	5%	-2:22	-2:93	-3:40		
	10%	-1:92	-2:66	-3:13		
Series		ES	Y	EI	RE	TR
Case -1	Russia	24.943***	0.921	1.634	12.841***	4.575
	India	35.526***	8.064	10.929*	38.126***	5.664
Case -2	Russia	14.009***	13.064***	17.198***	5.947	3.280
	India	11.267***	16.524***	9.383	15.748***	13.046***
Case -3	Russia	16.952***	12.243***	16.048**	3.780	3.101
	India	30.948***	5.748	7.150	11.332***	5.807
Asymptotic Critical Values of t-statistic						
		Case-1	Case-2	Case -3		
	1%	13.15	13.75	17.10		
	5%	9.53	10.17	12.82		
	10%	7.85	8.60	11.10		

Next, the study moved in investigating the long-run association between environmental sustainability, renewable energy consumption, environmental innovation and trade in the empirical model by performing [Bayer and Hanck \[53\]](#) combined cointegration test. The results of the cointegration

test reports are in Table V. study findings documented the rejection of the null hypothesis of no-cointegration at a 1% significance level, implying the long-run association between ES, RE, EI, and TR.

Table V Results of Bayer and Hanck combined cointegration test

Model	EG-JOH	EG-JOH-BO-BDM		EG-JOH	EG-JOH-BO-BDM
For Russia				For India	
$F_{ES}(ES RE, EI, TR)$	20.274***	46.612***		20.574***	57.409***
$F_{RE}(RE ES, RE, TR)$	13.49	65.256		14.455	57.903
$F_{EI}(EI ES, RE, TR)$	15.675	55.933		15.863	66.938
$F_{TR}(TR ES, RE, EI)$	16.021	58.817		15.906	61.31

Note: the superscript *** denotes the significant level at 1%.

Following, the study investigated the run cointegration between renewable energy, environmental sustainability, environmental innovation and trade by employing three tests through standard wald tests such as Fpass following [Pesaran, Shin \[60\]](#), tBDM test following [Banerjee, Dolado \[61\]](#) and Wpass with joint probability test under both symmetry and asymmetry assumption. The results of the symmetry and asymmetry cointegration test display in Table VI. Study findings documented that the test statistics of three cointegration tests were statistically significant at a 1% level of significance implying the rejection of null hypothesis of “no-cointegration”. Alternatively, study established long-run association in empirical model which is valid in both assumption that is symmetry and asymmetry.

Table VI Linear and Non-Linear Cointegration.

Russia				
Model	F _{pass}	tBDM	Wpass	Lag order
CO ₂ = Y Y ² , RE, EI, TR	5.751***	-12.512	15.241 ***	[1, 0, 0, 0, 0]
CO ₂ = Y Y ² , RE ⁺ , RE ⁻ , EI ⁺ , EI ⁻ , TR ⁺ , TR ⁻	27.979***	-7.2057***	8.2541 ***	[1,0,1,2,2,0,2,0,1]
India				
Model	F-statistics	BDM T-Stat		Lag order
CO ₂ = Y Y ² , RE, EI, TR	15.625****	-12.845***	12.551 ***	[1,1,1,1,1]
CO ₂ = Y Y ² , RE ⁺ , RE ⁻ , EI ⁺ , EI ⁻ , TR ⁺ , TR ⁻	9.1314****	-5.0264***	16.544 ***	[1,0,1,0,0,0,1,2,2]

Note: *** represents the significance level at 1%.

Long and short-run findings under a symmetry assumption

Table 3 report the empirical estimates for symmetric ARDL approaches. It is evident from the findings that empirical outcomes for GDP and GDP² are statistically significant in both country estimations. The positive coefficients for GDP and negative coefficient values for GDP² validate the EKC hypothesis for Russia and India. Our findings confirm that environmental quality initially deteriorates in both countries due to industrial activities but ultimately decreases after certain economic growth levels have been achieved. Also, the significant impact from RE is evident that

Refers to long-run estimation, the study documented a negative statistically significant association between renewable energy and environmental sustainability in Russia (a coefficient of -0.29146) and India (a coefficient of -0.09037), implying the integration and use of renewable energy play a critical in improving environmental quality. More precisely, an increase of 10% renewable energy application in aggregated energy consumption level can results in increased environmental quality in Russia by 2.9146% and India by 0.9037. in the short run, the nexus between renewable energy and

environmental sustainability established a negative association in Russia (a coefficient of -0.05755) and India (a coefficient of -0.04162). Study findings suggest that environmental quality in Russia has benefitted from integrating RE into the energy mix. At the same time, India needs further environmental reforms to increase renewable energy consumption to avoid climate change and higher carbon emissions in the coming decades. Our study findings are supported by existing literature see [Cuker, Chambers \[62\]](#), [Khan, Yu \[22\]](#), [Zafar, Shahbaz \[63\]](#), especially for long-run assessment. One possible justification is that Russia's recent economic reforms have put great pressure on the industrial sector to reach desired output levels, which in turn have contributed to environmental costs in the short run associated with further fewer efficiency gains from increased energy consumption

The coefficients of environmental innovation on environmental sustainability detected a negative statistically significant linkage between them both in the long-run and short-run in Russia (India). In the long run, a 10% development in environmental innovation assists in decreasing carbon emission by 2.7720% in Russia (by 1.246% in India) and in the short run, environmental quality be improved by 0.2856% in Russia (by 0.1298% in India) due to environmental innovation progress. Study findings suggest that by promoting environmental innovation in the economy, the adverse effects of carbon emission can be mitigated and moves to environmental sustainability. Our study findings align with existing literature see [Hao, Wu \[64\]](#), [Hussain and Dogan \[65\]](#), [Töbelmann and Wendler \[66\]](#). Environmental innovation (EI), particularly green technologies, are expected to be more carbon and energy-efficient and thus foster sustainable economic progress without dwindling the environmental ecosystem.

Next, we examine the coefficient values of trade (TR). The symmetric ARDL illustrate that a one percent increase in Trade Openness increases carbon emissions by 1.473 and 0.786 percent for Russia and India, respectively. The study argued that domestic trade liberalization increases pressure on energy consumption especially rely on fossil fuel increase the possibility for a higher level of carbon generation. However, the coefficients in the short run displayed negative statistically significant impacts on carbon emission for Russia (a coefficient of -0.0424) and India (a coefficient of -0.0926). It suggests that the integration of globalization and technology transfer contributes to fewer carbon emissions in the short run and positively correlates with energy efficiency.

Empirical model estimation passes through several residual diagnostic tests, namely autocorrelation, normality test, the test of heteroskadacity and the RESME test. Panel – C in Table VII reported the test statistics for residual tests. The p-value for test statistics is statistically insignificant, implying the empirical model reliability and efficiency in producing the magnitudes of the variables.

Table VII Symmetric effects in the long-run and short-run

Variables	Russin			India		
	Coefficient	std	t-stat	Coefficient	std	t-stat
Panel –A: Long-run coefficients						
GDP	0.2279***	0.0401402	5.677596	0.10035**	0.062576779	1.60363
GDP ²	-0.0614***	0.0044017	-13.9492	-0.407**	-0.24984454	1.629013
RE	-0.29146***	0.0581599	-5.01136	-0.090379**	0.062031226	-1.456992
EI	-0.277208***	0.0346623	-7.9974	-0.124617*	0.124033052	-1.004708
TR	0.147353***	0.0466388	3.159453	0.078416**	0.047649575	1.645681
Panel –B: short-run coefficients						
C	24.68759	3.5429143	6.968159	-2.758867	0.562756379	-4.902418
trend	-0.351043	0.0595446	-5.895468	-0.001454	0.001958795	-0.742293
GDP	0.1585***	0.0691672	2.291549	0.2966***	0.0632204	4.691525
GDP ²	-2.716***	1.2501076	-2.17261	-2.7415***	0.477488461	-5.7415
RE	-0.055755***	0.01923	-2.89811	-0.04162***	0.011428462	-3.641785

EI	-0.02856***	0.0065419	-4.3657	-0.012985***	0.001642213	-7.907014
TR	-0.042422***	-0.017461	-2.42951	-0.09265*	0.067308342	-1.376501
CointEq (-1)	-0.870381	0.1163803	-7.47876	-0.354914***	0.071011276	-4.997995
Residual diagnostic test						
χ^2_{Auto}	0.154			0.477		
χ^2_{Het}	0.152			0.577		
χ^2_{Nor}	0.452			0.485		
χ^2_{RESET}	0.745			0.522		
CUSUM	Stable			Stable		
CUSUMSQ	Stable			Stable		

Note: the superscript of ***/**/* denoted for the significant level at a 1%,5%, and 10%, respectively

Further, the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ (Fig. 2, Fig. 3, Fig. 4, Fig. 5) are also within critical bounds, which implies the constancy of the models.

Fig. 1. Linear ARDL CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graphs. (Russia)

Fig. 2. Linear ARDL CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graphs. (India)

Our findings in Table VIII for NARDL indicate that carbon emissions and economic growth have a positive statistically significant linkage for Russia (a coefficient of 0.0132) and India (a coefficient of 0.0954). In contrast, the coefficient estimates for Y nonlinearity are negative statistically significant for Russia (a coefficient -0.4652) and India (a coefficient of -1.745). Furthermore, refers to short-run assessment for EKC hypothesis study unveil positive tie between GDP and environmental sustainability and negative association between the nonlinear term of GDP and environmental sustainability. These outcomes support and confirm the presence of the EKC hypothesis in both empirical models in the short-run and long run.

Next, the empirical findings of nonlinear ARDL suggest that positive and negative renewable energy shocks exposed negative statistically linkage with environmental sustainability; that is, renewable energy expansion decreases CO₂ in India and Russia. More precisely, a 10% growth in renewable energy consumption leads to environmental sustainability in Russia (India) by reducing carbon emissions at a rate of 1.954% (4.01%). On the other hand, a 10% negative growth in renewable energy consumption accelerates environmental degradation by intensifying the carbon emission at a rate of 3.50% for Russia and 1.189% for India.

The analysis of energy innovation's positive and negative shocks presents negative statistically significant interlinkage with environmental sustainability. More precisely, 10% positive shocks on EI have reduced Russia's carbon emissions by 2.22%. On the other hand, 10% of negative shocks positively impact environmental quality, reducing carbon emission by 1.511% in Russia and 2.472% for India. In the short run, a 10% innovation in environmental, technological advancement can increase environmental sustainability by reducing carbon emission in Russia and India. In contrast, destructive policies in environmental innovation increase the environmental degradation for Russia by 1.856% and for India by 0.3951%. Study findings suggest that environmental innovation in terms of clean technological development assists in attaining an ecological balanced and efficient ecosystem. Furthermore, This is validated by the recent economic literature, which suggests that consistent environmental policies are crucial in increasing the impact of technological developments

The asymmetric ARDL suggests that positive and negative shocks in international trade increase carbon emissions by 0.019 and 0.115 for Russia and 0.1354 and 0.1152 for India. At the same time, the findings of the NARDL approach suggests that positive shocks in TR lead to higher carbon emissions in Russia (a coefficient of 0.188833) and in India (a coefficient of 0.06988). On the other hand,

a negative shock in trade liberalization is responsible for lower environmental degradation. It decreases carbon emissions into the atmosphere; however, the positive change has a much more profound impact. Portrays that It is noteworthy that the significant effect as these estimates indicate that the better integration between economic and environmental goals are critical in the short run as it enables emerging economies such as Russia and India to formulate long-term policy-making to protect the environment.

The availability of long-run and short-run asymmetry in empirical assessment was investigated by performing a standard wald test with the null hypothesis of “ symmetry”. The results of the standard wald test displayed in Panel-C and it is apparent that all the test statistics for both long-run (W_{LR}) and short-run (W_{SR}) are statistically significant at a 1% level of significance, implying the rejection of the null hypothesis. Alternatively, confirms the asymmetric association between environmental sustainability and explanatory variables. Furthermore, the empirical model construction and efficiency in estimation were confirmed with the results of residual diagnostic tests.

Table VIII Long-run short-run assessment under asymmetry

Variables	Coefficient	Std. error	t-stat		Coefficient	Std. error	t-stat	
Panel –A for long-run coefficients								
<i>For Russia</i>					<i>For India</i>			
Y	0.0132	0.005572	2.369008		0.0954	0.008882619	10.740076	
Q	-4.65E-02	0.0265806	-1.749399		-1.745	0.161951691	-10.774818	
RE_NEG	-0.350042	0.0591721	-5.915664		-0.111892	0.01952625	-5.730336	
RE_POS	-0.195497	0.039845	-4.906442		-0.400838	0.046969	-8.534097	
EI_POS	-0.222592	0.0290581	-7.660232		-0.353722	0.098361	-3.596161	
EI_NEG	-0.151106	0.065475	-2.307841		-0.247281	0.05288964	-4.675415	
TR_POS	0.188833	0.0548502	3.442707		0.069881	0.02723142	2.56619	
TR_NEG	0.387342	0.0757482	5.113544		0.16544	0.04326009	3.82431	
Panel –B: for short-run coefficients								
C	10.51053	5.4737041	1.920186		-0.381975	0.0355474	-10.745511	
@TREND	0.356836	0.4259894	0.837664		-0.040495	0.03495145	-1.158607	
ΔY	0.834178	0.18995	4.3915		0.203081	0.25021223	0.811635	
ΔQ	-0.1101	0.04702	-2.3424		-0.1945	0.11348963	-1.713813	
ΔRE_NEG	-0.0388	0.02201	-1.7622		-0.3011	0.11571948	-2.601982	
ΔRE_POS	0.09453	0.03239	2.918		-0.020688	0.01293846	-1.598954	
ΔEI_POS	-0.06497	0.02219	-2.927		-0.060597	0.04651732	-1.302676	
ΔEI_NEG	-0.185682	0.0693	-2.6772		-0.039156	0.01357957	-2.88345	
ΔTR_POS	-0.09974	0.0424	-2.3496		0.08458	0.0260713	3.244181	
ΔTR_NEG	0.15752	0.0415	3.79293		-0.06766	0.12289707	-0.55054	
CointEq(-1)*	-0.83418	0.120295	-6.93443		-0.20308	0.03135664	-6.47649	
Panel –C: Test of symmetry and Residual Diagnostic test								
W_{LR}^{ES}	12.485					9.225		
W_{LR}^{RE}	9.342					6.745		
W_{LR}^{EI}	11.641					7.552		
W_{LR}^{TR}	14.231					10.221		

χ^2_{Auto}	0.451					0.485	
χ^2_{Het}	0.751					0.442	
χ^2_{Nor}	0.422					0.785	
χ^2_{RESET}	0.354					0.215	

Note: the superscript of ***/**/* denoted for the significant level at a 1%,5%, and 10%, respectively

Fig. 3. Nonlinear ARDL CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graphs. (Russia)

Fig. 4. Nonlinear ARDL CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graphs. (India)

The multipliers for both variables are plotted in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, which portray adjustment to a new equilibrium after positive and negative shocks. The black dotted line indicates the nonlinear adjustment of CO₂ to negative shocks, while the solid black line portrays the adjustment of CO₂ to a positive shock. The asymmetric pattern indicated by the red dotted line is the difference between both negative and positive shocks.

Fig. 5(c). Nonlinear ARDL dynamic multiplier effect graphs (Russia)

Fig.6.Nonlinear ARDL dynamic multiplier effect graphs (India)

Next, the study implemented a non-granger causality test in the panel form by following the framework proposed by Toda and Yamamoto [67]. The results of the causality test displayed in Table IX with the panel –A(B) for Russia (India), and several directional casualties were detected. Our estimation has established the bidirectional causality between economic growth and environment sustainability and Russia's environmental innovation and economic growth. On the other hand, the study revealed bidirectional causality between renewable energy and environmental sustainability [RE \leftrightarrow ES], total trade and renewable energy [TR \leftrightarrow RE], and total trade and environmental innovation [TR \leftrightarrow EI]. Furthermore, the study documented several unidirectional casualties among research variables, including environmental innovation, renewable energy and environmental sustainability, and total trade to environmental sustainability. Study findings suggest that addressing the association and impact of all selected explanatory variables in the study is imperative for achieving environmental sustainability.

Table IX Toda-Yamamoto causality test $d_{max}=2$

	ES	Y	RE	EI	Trade	
Panel-A: Russia						$Y \leftrightarrow ES$; $RE \rightarrow ES$; $EI \rightarrow ES$; $TR \rightarrow ES$; $RE \rightarrow Y$; $EI \leftarrow Y$; $EI \rightarrow RE$; $TR \rightarrow RE$; $Y \rightarrow TR$
ES	-	4.607***	4.8827***	4.9402***	2.2711**	
Y	7.1771***	-	1.8929*	1.9142*	0.1004	
RE	0.9171	1.2842	-	5.1449***	7.962***	
EI	0.4245	2.6654**	0.213	-	1.3488	
TR	0.4546	20.0255***	0.0812	0.0376	-	
Panel -B: for India						$Y \rightarrow ES$; $RE \leftarrow ES$; $EI \rightarrow ES$; $TR \leftarrow ES$; $RE \rightarrow Y$; $TR \leftarrow RE$; $TR \leftarrow EI$;
ES	-	6.013***	10.4195***	19.8242***	3.1729**	
Y	0.3146	-	7.0826***	1.6615	0.0433	
RE	4.2618***	1.6641	-	1.0094	3.4197***	
EI	0.6655	2.0232	1.4468	-	16.3158***	
TR	16.9836***	1.6568	3.8977***	8.849***	-	

Note: the superscript ***/**/* denoted the level of significant at a 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Causalities between environmental sustainability (ES), renewable energy consumption (RE), environmental innovation (EI), economic growth (Y), and Trade (TR) (Russia)

Causalities between environmental sustainability (ES), renewable energy consumption (RE), environmental innovation (EI), economic growth (Y), and Trade (TR) (India)

Discussion

The empirical evidence for the existence of the EKC hypothesis through symmetric and asymmetric methodologies is in contrast to [Mrabet, AlSamara \[68\]](#) and [Charfeddine \[69\]](#). However, our findings align with [Al-mulali, Weng-Wai \[70\]](#), who investigate a panel of high-income group countries. Our empirical estimates show that the GDP coefficients are positive to environmental sustainability, which documents that economic growth takes precedence in Russia and India; it drives human demands and is also the primary reason for ecological problems. These outcomes were expected as the recent ecological footprint of Russia and India has significantly increased along with its GDP. Also, these countries in recent years have overseen the transformation of the quality of life, and more and more people have access to better sanitation, health, food, and other necessities. However, this massive scale of economic progress has impacted daily lifestyles and has increased demand for natural resources beyond the necessities of basic needs; this, in turn, leads to pressure on environmental quality. The negative coefficient of GDP² indicates that the achievement of certain economic goals and prosperity, environmental quality in Russia and India can be improved through structural changes in the domestic economy, innovation in environmental technologies and integration of environmental reform within the economic policies as [Dogan, Ulucak \[46\]](#) argued that advanced environmental technologies and stringent regulations minimize the ecological footprint in emerging economies.

The current study also presents empirical outcomes between renewable energy consumption and environmental sustainability in Russia and India. In recent economic literature, several studies have provided support for renewable energy consumption to reduce environmental degradation. Among these, [Bhattacharya, Awaworyi Churchill \[71\]](#) used a panel dataset for 85 developed and developing economies to articulate that growth in renewable energy gas has a significant impact on environmental quality and economic growth, especially in developing economies. Likewise, [Hu, Xie \[72\]](#) selected 25 developing economies and used FMOLS and DOLS to indicate that effective implementation of renewable energy leads to lower carbon emissions over the long run. In support of these outcomes, [Dogan, Ulucak \[46\]](#) selected SSA countries to explore the association between environmental pollution and renewable energy during the time scale of 1980-2011. They found that higher fossil fuels consumption contributes to environmental pollution, while renewable energy harms environmental degradation. However, [Apergis and Cooray \[73\]](#) contradicted these findings for a panel of 29 developing economies to report that renewable energy positively correlates with carbon emissions because of inadequate storage technology to deal with supply constraints. For Vietnam, [Al-Mulali and Ozturk \[74\]](#) highlighted that a lower share of renewable energy consumption means that renewable energy had no significant impact on carbon emissions. [Khoshnevis Yazdi and Shakouri \[75\]](#) also reported similar outcomes.

Several empirical studies have recently explored the association between environmental innovation and carbon emission to capture the effects of renewable energy with patents and R&D expenditure as the main proxy variable being used. The findings of empirical literature remain inconclusive. In a comprehensive study, [Fernández-Amador, Oberdabernig \[76\]](#) investigated the association between carbon emission and innovation in environmental technologies to conclude that environmental technologies effectively reduce carbon emissions over the long and short run. In recent years, [Awaworyi Churchill, Inekwe \[77\]](#) explored the association between renewable energy, environmental technologies, and carbon emission to report mixed findings for different countries over the different periods and argued that the association between environmental technologies and carbon emissions is significantly dependent upon the application of environmental legislation. Several studies such as [Acemoglu, Gancia \[78\]](#) and [Jaffe, Newell \[79\]](#) have argued that limitation of carbon emissions through environmental technologies is dependent upon country-specific characteristics and further explained that these effects rebound over time and negatively affect the accumulation of long-term environmental goals through innovation in green technologies [\[80\]](#).

Lastly, we investigate the empirical association between environmental sustainability and trade openness. In the last two decades, several studies have explored such association and how it affects economic growth over the long run. [Obradović and Lojanica \[81\]](#) investigated the association between trade, carbon emissions, and energy consumption for southeastern European countries through the VECM approach to discover the long-run causal association between energy consumption, carbon emissions, and trade openness. However, the authors found no short-term causality between trade and carbon emissions for Bulgaria and Greece. [Cherni and Essaber Jouini \[82\]](#) furthered the research by using the ARDL approach to examine how trade affects carbon emissions or vice versa for Russia. The researchers used the granger causality test to report long and short-term causal associations and their direction. The empirical analysis revealed the bidirectional causality between trade and carbon emissions and trade and renewable energy consumption; however, it found no causality between renewable energy consumption and carbon emissions. In another study, [Kais and Sami \[83\]](#) investigated energy consumption and trade effects over carbon emissions for 58 emerging and developed economies from 1990 to 2012. The authors developed three panels, i.e., Latin America and Caribbean, north Asian region, and Europe. The empirical analysis indicated that carbon emissions and energy consumption have positive for all three panels. The researchers reported similar trade and carbon emissions estimates, and its statistical value was significant for north Asia and Europe. Lastly, the researchers also confirmed the existence of a u-shaped curve for trade and carbon emissions.

5. Conclusion

The current study has attempted to investigate the dynamic association between environmental sustainability, trade openness, income, environmental innovation, and renewable energy for Russia and India. It compares the influence of the variables above in these economies. To analyze this nexus, we applied both conventional unit root tests following dickey [Dickey and Fuller \[47\]](#), perron [Phillips and Perron \[59\]](#), [Kwiatkowski, Phillips \[84\]](#) and [Zivot and Andrews \[52\]](#) and nonlinear unit root test following [Kruse \[50\]](#) and [Kapetanios, Shin \[51\]](#). The long-run association was evaluated by performing a combined cointegration test proposed by [Bayer and Hanck \[53\]](#), and symmetry and asymmetry nexus were gauged by implementing ARDL and NARDL. Finally, the directional association was investigated by employing the non-granger causality framework proposed by [Toda and Yamamoto \[67\]](#). The key findings of this study as follows:

Our empirical approach allows us to provide useful econometric findings. It is evident from the empirical estimates for asymmetric [\[12\]](#) and symmetric ARDL approaches [\[60\]](#) that GDP and GDP² are significant under both empirical approaches. The positive coefficients for GDP and negative coefficient values for GDP² validate the EKC hypothesis for Russia and India. Initially, environmental quality deteriorates in both countries due to higher industrial activities but ultimately decreases after certain economic growth levels have been achieved. We further disclose that for Russia, renewable energy (RE) and environmental innovation (EI) reduce carbon emissions, while trade (TR) has a positive association with environmental degradation. However, in the asymmetric ARDL findings, positive (RE⁺) and negative (EI⁻) contribute to environmental degradation. For India, the empirical estimates (ARDL) for renewable energy (RE), environmental innovation (EI) and trade (TR) report similar findings as Russia. However, the findings for NARDL reveal that negative changes in trade (TR⁻) contribute to environmental degradation.

These findings suggest that policymakers in Russia and India must introduce institutional and environmental reforms to cohesively between domestic and foreign investors. These policies will also allow these emerging economies to take advantage of globalization and higher integration between international trade and foreign direct investment. Additionally, policy changes aimed at lower tax and related investives will allow these investors to promote investments in green energy projects. However, higher taxation and restrictions on outdated technologies will prevent environmental degradation.

We further document that for Russia, causality runs from GDP and RE towards CO₂ emissions, whereas for India, there is a causal association between environmental innovation and trade towards CO₂ emissions. This causal association proposes that further ecological policies must promote energy efficiency and energy conservation through better ecological technologies. Furthermore, the share of

renewable energy in the energy mix must be increased to minimize the negative effects on the environmental footprint. In this regard, higher investments in green energy technologies will effectively reduce environmental damage from fossil fuel consumption. Additionally, the higher share of fossil fuels in the energy mix must be minimized by adding low pollution natural gas. Lastly, reforms in pricing strategies must be considered as a policy mechanism to increase renewable energy consumption in both Russia and India.

Finally, although the current study significantly contributes to the existing economic literature; however, we have been unable to account for the association between carbon emissions and structural changes in Russia and India. These economies rely significantly on informal economies. Further research is required to evaluate the association between industrial competitiveness and microenterprises and how recent economic and environmental policies have affected them. Hence, we encourage future studies to assess these policies for the studied economy. These policies are a key factor in reaching future international climate control agreements in developing economies.

Declaration

- Ethics approval and consent to participate
Not applicable
- Consent to Participate
“Not applicable”
- Consent for publication
“Not applicable”
- Availability of data and materials
The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.
- Competing interests
The authors declare that they have no competing interests."
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